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Susceptibility of olive cultivars and selections to *Colletotrichum* species causing anthracnose in Spain

Anabel Exposito-Diaz,^{1†} Boris X. Camiletti,^{2†} M. Teresa Garcia-Lopez,¹ Diego Cabello,¹ Dov Prusky,³ Concepción M. Diez,¹ and Juan Moral^{1*}

¹Department of Agronomy, Maria de Maeztu Excellence Unit, University of Cordoba. Edif. C4, Campus de Rabanales, Cordoba, 14071, Spain.

²Department of Crop Sciences, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, Urbana, IL 61801, USA.

³Department of Postharvest Science, Agricultural Research Organization, Rishon LeTzion, Israel

*Corresponding author: juan.moral@uco.es

† These authors contributed equally to the present manuscript

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Abstract

Anthracnose, the most critical fruit disease affecting olive crops, necessitates the evaluation of the susceptibility of traditional and new varieties. In Spain and Portugal, Anthracnose is caused by several *Colletotrichum* species, with *C. godetiae* and *C. nymphaeae* being dominant and *C. acutatum* and *C. fioriniae* being secondary. This study explores the susceptibility of fruits from an F1 progeny resulting from a cross between 'Picual' (resistant) and 'Arbequina' (moderately susceptible) cultivars to *C. godetiae*. While most genotypes showed resistance levels comparable to their parents, seven showed a 50% reduction in disease severity compared to 'Picual.' The normal distribution of genotypes' response to the pathogen suggests a complex resistance mechanism. Furthermore, we assessed the susceptibility of four traditional cultivars, two new cultivars ('Sikitita-2' and 'Martina'), and five advanced selections (pre-commercial genotypes) to *C. godetiae* and *C. nymphaeae*. Despite the significant interaction between the olive genotype and *Colletotrichum* species in this experiment, the new cultivars and advanced selections were classified as susceptible or moderately susceptible against both species. A subsequent analysis of the interaction between 'Picual' (resistant) and 'Hojiblanca' (susceptible) fruits with the four mentioned *Colletotrichum* species revealed significant differences among cultivars but no interaction between genotype and pathogen species. *Colletotrichum* species were categorized as follows: i) *C. godetiae* and *C. nymphaeae* as highly virulent, ii) *C. acutatum* as moderately virulent, and iii) *C. fioriniae* as weakly virulent. Finally, *C. nymphaeae* exhibited an enhanced ability to infect and develop acervuli in olive leaves, potentially serving as an inoculum source for this species. The absence of a correlation between leaf and fruit susceptibilities to the pathogen suggests differences in resistance mechanisms. In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the complex interactions between olive genotype and *Colletotrichum* species, essential for cultivar selection and understanding the disease cycle.

Keywords: olive genotypes, resistance, cultivar interaction, disease severity, virulence.

The olive tree (*Olea europaea* subsp. *europaea* var. *sativa*) is the most widespread tree crop globally. Numerous collections of olive genetic resources have been created globally, spanning the traditional olive-growing regions like the Mediterranean and extending to newer areas like North and South America, Australia, China, and South Africa (Bartolini et al. 2005). The World Olive Germplasm Bank of Cordoba (WOGBC) in Spain, established in 1970, stands as one of the largest repositories, housing 499 accessions from 21 countries (Caballero et al. 2006). Spain is the world leader in olive oil and table olive-fruit production, with more than 272 olive cultivars covering an area of 2.6 million hectares (Trujillo et al., 2014). Notably, Italy, Greece, Portugal, and several other countries also contribute significantly to olive production (Espadas-Aldana et al., 2019). Anthracnose, caused by numerous *Colletotrichum* species, is the most critical fungal disease affecting olive fruits (Cacciola et al., 2012). This disease leads to annual yield losses of up to 40% in humid areas, where susceptible cultivars predominate (Cacciola et al., 2012; Talhinhos et al., 2018). Furthermore, *Colletotrichum* not only reduces olive yield but also diminishes the quality of the oils obtained from the affected fruit. Anthracnose causes sensorial defects in the olive oil and chemical detrimental effects, such as an increase in free acidity, the peroxide index and the content of aldehydes, a decrease in oxidative stability and the content of polyphenols and α -tocoferol, and changes to the alkyl ester composition. The fatty acid composition, however, is not altered (Carvalho et al., 2008; Iannotta et al., 1999; Moral et al., 2014; Runcio et al., 2008). Additionally, it has

been indicated that biologically active fungal secondary metabolites can contaminate the oil during the extraction process (Riolo et al., 2023a).

The pathogen conidia cause latent infection in developing and unripe olive fruits throughout the season. During the fall-winter period, as asymptomatic fruits change color from deep green to yellowish and then purple, they begin to show typical necrotic and depressed lesions that release an orange gelatinous substance embedding numerous conidia under humid conditions (Moral and Trapero 2009; 2012; Romero et al., 2017). The breaking of the fruit epidermis by the pathogen leads to dehydration and eventual mummification of the affected fruits. Subsequently, the pathogen colonizes fruit peduncles, resulting in most affected fruits falling off (Graniti et al., 1993). Beyond fruit rot, olives may exhibit a second syndrome characterized by necrotic leaves, which can lead to shoot and branch dieback. This syndrome has been associated with the production of toxins by the pathogen in rotten fruits, which were hypothesized to be transported to twigs and leaves (Moral et al., 2009). Riolo et al. (2023a) have recently demonstrated that *Colletotrichum* species produce 29 metabolites in rotten olive fruits, including compounds with phytotoxic and cytotoxic activity. In Portugal, Talhinhos et al. (2011) also reported direct infection of olive leaves and shoots by the pathogen, suggesting that these tissues may serve as inoculum sources, although this remains understudied (Garcia-Lopez et al., 2023). The susceptibility of leaves and twigs to anthracnose infections and their role as an inoculum source was reported since the first studies of this disease and were confirmed more recently using molecular diagnostic tests (Graniti et al., 1993; Cacciola et al. 2012; Schena et al., 2017). Although the ability of these tissues to act as a source of inoculum for the pathogen is highly dependent on the ability of the fungus to produce fruiting bodies (acervuli) in these olive tissues (Moral et al., 2009). Traditional

management of olive anthracnose involves using copper-based fungicides (Cacciola et al., 2012). Nevertheless, this approach may prove insufficient under favorable disease conditions, leading to potential copper accumulation in the soil (Moral et al., 2018). Farmers often decide on early harvesting in anthracnose endemic regions, affecting yield and oil characteristics (Moral et al., 2014).

Eighteen *Colletotrichum* species contribute to the olive anthracnose, belonging to three species complexes: *C. acutatum*, *C. gloeosporioides*, and *C. boninense* (Moral et al., 2021; Schena et al., 2014; Talhinhos et al., 2018). Given the polyphagous nature of this genus, Moral et al. (2021) proposed that native *Colletotrichum* species transitioned from wild hosts to olives during crop expansion. Subsequently, the species that primarily colonizes the crop and eventually becomes dominant is challenged to be displaced by other species, an ecological phenomenon known as the 'priority effect' (Garcia-Lopez et al., 2023). Consequently, although several *Colletotrichum* species can coexist in each olive-growing region, typically, one species emerges as dominant while the others are secondary (Garcia-Lopez et al., 2023; Moral et al., 2015; Talhinhos et al., 2018). In many regions of Portugal, *C. nymphaeae* is the most common species causing olive anthracnose, while in Italy, *C. acutatum* has been identified as the primary species associated with the disease. In Greece and many regions of Spain, *C. godetiae* prevails (Moral et al., 2021; Talhinhos et al., 2015; Schena et al., 2017).

The resistance of olive genotypes to the pathogen plays a crucial role in managing anthracnose (Moral et al., 2017). The analysis of genotype-pathogen interactions, encompassing diverse olive genotypes evaluated against different *Colletotrichum* species, facilitates a comprehensive assessment of the resistance stability of genotypes.

From an agronomic point of view, evaluating the resistance level of olive cultivars against the dominant pathogenic species is crucial (Moral et al., 2017). Under controlled conditions, Talhinhos et al. (2015) evaluated the susceptibility of eight Portuguese cultivars to pathogenic species belonging to the *C. acutatum* and *C. gloeosporioides* species complexes. They reported a significant interaction between cultivars and *Colletotrichum* species and high variability in virulence among *Colletotrichum* species. Similarly, Riolo et al. (2023b) and Licciardello et al. (2022) performed inoculations on olive fruits of Italian cultivars and exposed them to different *Colletotrichum* species. These studies also revealed significant variations in virulence among fungal species and resistance among olive cultivars.

The most extensive evaluation of olive cultivars for resistance to the pathogen was carried out at the Worldwide Olive Germplasm Bank of Cordoba (WOGB), Spain, over three seasons with high disease pressure (Moral et al., 2017). Thus, we systematically assessed the natural infections caused by *C. godetiae*, the predominant pathogen in the region (Moral et al., 2021). A visual evaluation of the fruit-rot incidence for each olive tree was performed using a 0-10 rating scale (Moral et al., 2009). The study categorized over 300 cultivars worldwide into five groups: highly susceptible, susceptible, moderately susceptible, resistant, and highly resistant. Representative cultivars were identified for each category, with 'Picual' and 'Arbequina' being selected as representatives for resistant and moderately susceptible groups, respectively (Moral et al., 2017). Similarly, Moral et al. (2015) classified the resistance of a group of advanced selections, encompassing new genotypes with desired agronomic traits and their progenitors under controlled and field conditions. Notably, this latter evaluation revealed increased resistance in genotypes derived from the resistant parental lines 'Frantoio' and 'Picual'

(Moral et al., 2015). However, resistance to other *Colletotrichum* species capable of causing anthracnose, including the predominant ones, remains unknown.

Since the mid-1990s, the University of Cordoba (UCO) has carried out an olive breeding program with the primary goal of developing new genotypes with advanced traits, including early bearing, high yield, increased oil content, adaptability to mechanized harvesting, and resistance to diseases (Rallo et al., 2018). The evaluation strategy for these genotypes includes three key steps: an initial evaluation of F₁ progenies, an evaluation of preliminary selections, and a subsequent evaluation of advanced selections (Rallo et al., 2018). In breeding programs for self-incompatible tree crops, identifying the resistance of the F₁ progeny to pathogens is critical for understanding the underlying mechanisms of plant response (Cubero 2013). However, our understanding of the heritability of resistance to *Colletotrichum* in olives remains limited, mainly due to the long period (8-10 years) required for seedlings to produce drupes for inoculation experiments (Rallo et al., 2018). Furthermore, given the expansion of olive groves in regions prone to anthracnose, it is imperative to assess the resistance of new genotypes to the pathogen before considering their commercialization (Moral et al., 2015).

Therefore, the objectives of this study were to investigate (i) the variability of susceptibility to *C. godetiae* in F₁ progeny ('Picual' × 'Arbequina'), (ii) the variability of susceptibility to both *C. godetiae* and *C. nymphaeae* in new cultivars, advanced selections, and commercial olive genotypes; (iii) the interaction between olive genotype and *Colletotrichum* species; and (iv) the leaf response of two main cultivars to the dominant species of the pathogen.

Materials and methods

Fungal isolates

Reference *Colletotrichum* isolates, previously well characterized and identified using a multilocus approach (ITS, TUB2, ACT, CHS-1, HIS3, and GAPDH) (Moral et al., 2021), were sourced from the mycological collection of the Agronomy Department at UCO and used throughout this study. The isolates included *C. acutatum* (Col-536), *C. fioriniae* (Col-693), *C. godetiae* (Col-556 and Col-502), and *C. nymphaeae* (Col-451 and Col-151).

Variability of susceptibility to *Colletotrichum godetiae* in olive fruits of F₁ progenies ('Picual' × 'Arbequina')

Approximately 4,000 fruits corresponding to the 81-85 phenological stage (green-yellowish fruits) according to the BBCH scale (Sanz-Cortes et al., 2002) were harvested from 52 F₁ genotypes and their parents in October 2020. The harvested drupes were stored at 4°C until use. The F₁ genotypes were obtained by crossing the resistant cultivar 'Picual' (female parent) and the moderately susceptible 'Arbequina' (male parent) as part of the olive breeding program at the University of Cordoba (UCO). The genotypes were established across different commercial plots owned by Balam Agriculture, Frutaria, and Todolivo Andalusia, southern Spain, between 2012 and 2014.

The isolate Col-556 (*C. godetiae*) was selected for the experiments. Conidial suspensions, obtained from a 7-day-old pure culture on PDA (Potato Dextrose Agar, Difco, Darmstadt, Germany) with lactic acid (0.05%) at 20 °C, were obtained by scraping the colony surface with a scalpel followed by filtration through a double-layered sterile cheesecloth to remove mycelium pieces. The resulting suspensions were transferred to

250-ml Erlenmeyer flasks and adjusted to 5×10^5 conidia/ml. Fruits were gently washed three times by immersion in tap water containing Tween 20 (0.02%) to ensure the effective removal of residual fungicides. Surface disinfection was then conducted using a commercial bleach solution (Cl at 50 g/liter, 10% concentration), followed by air drying on a sterile surface inside a laminar flow hood. Only fruits without mechanical damage or insect-induced wounds were used. For inoculation, 60 fruits of each genotype were placed in humid plastic chambers (100% RH), each measuring $22 \times 16 \times 10$ cm (20 fruits per chamber). The experimental design comprised three blocks and three different conidial suspensions. Each fruit was sprayed with 8 ml conidial suspension containing 5×10^5 conidia/ml, corresponding to around 0.4 ml per fruit. Similarly, non-inoculated controls were sprayed with distilled water (0.4 ml per fruit). Following inoculations, the chambers were maintained at $22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ under fluorescent lighting (12-h photoperiod, $40 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ intensity).

Disease severity was assessed weekly over the subsequent 30 days post-inoculation, employing a 0-5 rating scale, where 0 = no visible symptoms, 1 = visible symptoms on less than 25% of the fruit surface, 2 = visible symptoms on 26-50% of the surface, 3 = visible-symptoms on 51-75% of the surface, 4 = visible-symptoms on 76-99% of the surface, and 5 = completely rotted fruit (100%), with abundant conidia showing the typical pinkish-orange gelatinous pustules (soapy fruit) (Moral et al., 2008). Severity values from 0 to 5 for each replicate were used to calculate the Disease Severity Index (DSI) applying McKinney's formula (1923): $\text{DSI} = [(\sum ni \times i) / N] \times 100$, where 'i' is the severity (0-5), 'ni' is the number of fruits with a severity of 'i', and 'N' is the total number of fruits. The data were further used to calculate the Relative Area Under the Disease Progress Curve (rAUDPC)

by trapezoidal integration of DSI values over time, as described by Campbell and Madden (1990).

Variability in susceptibility to *C. godetiae* and *C. nymphaeae* in fruits of four commercial olive cultivars, two new cultivars, and five advanced selections

In November 2020 (2020/21 season), fruits from two new cultivars and five advanced selections (approximately 4,000 each), i.e., pre-commercial olive genotypes, were harvested at the final evaluation in the breeding program conducted by the Agronomy Department at the UCO, Spain. Again, the fruits were at the 81-85 BBCH-phenological growth stage (Sanz-Cortes et al., 2002) and were stored at 4°C until use. The new cultivars 'Sikitita-2' (code UC-I 2-35) and 'Martina' (code UC-I 2-68) and advanced selections UC-I 6-9, UC-I 7-8, UC-I 33-23, UC-I 42-61, and UC-I 44-69 were obtained from reciprocal crosses between 'Arbequina' (moderately susceptible) and 'Picual' (resistant) or from open pollination of these progenitors. At the same time, the commercial cultivars Arbequina, Hojiblanca, Picual, and Sikitita were evaluated as controls. These genotypes were previously classified as resistant ('Picual'), moderately susceptible ('Arbequina' and 'Sikitita'), and susceptible ('Hojiblanca') (Moral et al., 2017). The studied genotypes were planted in research plots within the WOGB in Cordoba, Spain. The reference strains of *C. godetiae* (Col-556) and *C. nymphaeae* (Col-451) were used (Moral et al., 2021). Conidial suspensions, fruit surface disinfection, and inoculations were performed as detailed above. All the *Colletotrichum* strains were inoculated separately on the fruits using three replicate humid chambers with 20 fruits per replication and stored at $22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. As in the previous study by Moral and Trapero 2009, disease severity was

assessed weekly for 37 days, as described previously. The Relative Area rAUDPC was calculated by trapezoidal integration of DSI values over 30 days.

Pathogenic interaction between commercial olive cultivar and *Colletotrichum* species

In January 2021 (2020/21 season), approximately 4,000 fruits were harvested from the widely distributed traditional olive cultivars 'Hojiblanca' (susceptible) and 'Picual' (resistant) (Moral et al., 2015, 2017), established in the WOGB of the UCO. In this case, four well-characterized fungal strains were used: *C. acutatum* (Col-536), *C. fioriniae* (Col-693), *C. godetiae* (Col-556), and *C. nymphaeae* (Col-451) (Moral et al., 2021). Conidial suspensions and fruit inoculations were prepared and performed as detailed above, with the different isolates being separately inoculated onto the fruits placed in the humid chambers. Disease severity was evaluated weekly for 30 days, following the methodology described in the previous experiments.

Variability in susceptibility to *C. godetiae* and *C. nymphaeae* in olive leaves of six commercial cultivars

In mid-March 2023, young and adult leaves (i.e., leaves from the third node and fully expanded leaves from the sixth node) from commercial cultivars 'Arbequina', 'Frantoio', 'Hojiblanca', 'Ocal', 'Picual', and 'Sikitita' established at the WOGB of the UCO were harvested. The leaves were washed with tap water and Tween 20 (0.02%), air dried on a sterile surface in a laminar flow hood and placed in humid chambers (20 adult and 20 young leaves per chamber and three replicate chambers plus one control chamber per cultivar). The fungal strains Col-502 (*C. godetiae*) and Col-151 (*C. nymphaeae*) were selected for inoculation (Moral et al., 2021). Sixteen milliliters of a conidial suspension of 2×10^5 conidia/ml were sprayed over the 40 leaves in each humid chamber, resulting in

an approximate treatment of 0.4 ml per leaf. As a control treatment, three additional chambers containing leaves were sprayed with distilled water (0.4 ml per leaf). All chambers were incubated for 4 days at $22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ under fluorescent light (12-h photoperiod, $40 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) and high humidity to enhance spore germination and pathogen infection.

After that, leaves were surface-disinfected with commercial bleach (Cl at 50 g/liter, 10% solution) for 1 min to remove any non-infecting conidia from the leaf surface. The surface-disinfected leaves were then replaced in the same chambers (previously disinfected) and incubated under the prior conditions for 15 days to allow colonization of the leaf tissue. Following the incubation period, the percentage of the necrotic surface of each leaf was estimated visually according to Palti (1949). In addition, the percentage of leaves showing pathogen acervuli (Fig. 1 Supplementary) was evaluated using a stereoscopic microscope at $50\times$ magnification (Leica MZ10F). Finally, the internal colonization of the leaf by the pathogen was evaluated. For this measurement, small tissue sections ($\approx 20 \text{ mm}^2$, five sections per leaf) from inoculated leaves (without external symptoms) were superficially disinfected (Cl at 50 g/liter, 10% solution, for 1 min, and 70% EtOH for 1 min) and cultured on Petri dishes containing PDA acid (with lactic acid at 0.05%) medium supplemented with two fungicides (20 ppm iprodione and 100 ppm cupric sulfate) and two antibiotics (100 ppm streptomycin sulfate and 100 ppm aureomycin). Fungicides were added to the media to inhibit the growth of *Alternaria* species, a prominent contaminant on olive leaves, as this genus is extremely sensitive to iprodione. Conversely, *Colletotrichum* is less sensitive to this fungicide and resistant to Cu^{++} (Moral et al., 2009). For each cultivar and developmental stage (young and adult), leaf sections were collected, consisting of three replicates, two leaves per replicate, and five sections per leaf. Leaf sections were incubated in Petri dishes for 7 days as described above.

Subsequently, the number of *Colletotrichum* colonies grown on the leaf pieces was recorded, and the percentage of colonized pieces was determined.

Statistical analysis

The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to determine whether the severity data (rAUDPC) of the F₁ genotypes followed a normal distribution. Additionally, Levene's test was used to verify the homogeneity of variances of the severity data, and arcsine transformation was applied when necessary. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed on the data, with experimental replicates serving as blocks. Treatment means were compared using Least Significant Difference (LSD) test at a significance level of $P \leq 0.05$. Furthermore, Kaplan-Meier survival curves were estimated, with days after inoculation as the time variable, incidence as the event variable, and olive genotype or *Colletotrichum* species as the group. Kaplan-Meier percentiles (i.e., 10, 25, 50, 75, and 90%) were calculated, and survival curves were compared using the nonparametric Logrank test. In the leaf inoculation experiment, our primary focus was comparing the resistance of different olive genotypes and the virulence of both *Colletotrichum* species. Cultivar resistances were assessed through ANOVA for each combination of leaf type (young and adult) and pathogen species.

Similarly, ANOVAs were conducted to examine the virulence of each pathogen species for each leaf type, with the cultivars serving as blocks. Percentage data were arcsine transformed to ensure equal variances and normality. Nonparametric Spearman correlations were performed to assess the relationship between dependent variables. All data from the experiments were analyzed using Statistix 10 (Analytical Software, Tallahassee, FL) or SPSS Software (version 29.0; SPSS Inc., Chicago).

Results

Variability in susceptibility to *Colletotrichum godetiae* in olive fruits of F₁ progenies ('Picual' × 'Arbequina')

Thirty-seven days post-inoculation, the fruits of the 52 tested F₁ genotypes and their parents showed no immunity. All genotypes displayed fruit rot symptoms caused by the *C. godetiae* isolate, albeit at varying disease severity levels. This included fruit from the moderately susceptible 'Arbequina' and the typically resistant 'Picual'. However, seven genotypes showed an average disease severity (measured by rAUDPC) of less than 10%, while 'Picual' showed a severity of 21.5%. Conversely, olive fruits from 30 genotypes exhibited an average disease severity falling within classes ranging from 40% to 88%, surpassing that of the moderately susceptible cultivar Arbequina (37%). The analysis of severity data followed a normal distribution, as indicated by the Shapiro-Wilk's P-values (Fig. 1, $P = 0.369$). As expected, the parental genotypes displayed varying responses to *C. godetiae*, with the 'Picual' cultivar showing higher resistance ($P \leq 0.05$) than the 'Arbequina' cultivar. Among the F₁ progenies, those with a 40-48% disease severity were the most frequent (19%).

Variability in susceptibility to *C. godetiae* and *C. nymphaeae* in fruits of four commercial olive cultivars, two new cultivars, and five advanced selections

Anthracoze symptoms were detected on fruits of the genotypes 'Hojiblanca', 'Sikitita', UC-I 6-9, UC-I 7-8, UC-I 33-23, UC-I 42-61, and UC-I 44-69 at 7 days post-inoculation when inoculated with *C. godetiae*. Fruit of the 'Hojiblanca', UC-I 6-9, UC-I 7-8, UC-I 42-61, and UC-I 44-69 genotypes inoculated with *C. nymphaeae* showed symptoms within a comparable period (7 days). There were marked differences in disease severity among

olive genotypes depending on the *Colletotrichum* species. For instance, the 'Picual' fruits, when inoculated with the *C. godetiae* and *C. nymphaeae* isolates, showed a disease severity (rAUDPC) of 12.7% and 21.5%, respectively (mean of 17.1%). In contrast, those of the new cultivar Sikitita-2 exhibited disease severity percentages of 32.6% and 10.3%, respectively (mean of 21.5%; Table 1). ANOVAs revealed significant differences in susceptibility among olive genotypes and a significant effect of the interaction between olive genotype and *Colletotrichum* species ($P < 0.001$).

Given the interest in classifying genotypes based on resistance to the pathogen, the susceptibility of the new genotypes was compared independently following inoculation with *C. godetiae* and *C. nymphaeae* (Table 1). Thus, olive genotypes formed seven homogeneous groups based on the disease severity caused by *C. nymphaeae*, with fruits of 'Sikitita-2' being significantly more resistant than those of genotypes UC-I 6-9, UC-I 7-8, UC-I 33-23, UC-I 44-69, UC-I 42-61, 'Martina', 'Arbequina', and 'Hojiblanca'. Remarkably, olive fruits of the resistant cultivar 'Picual' showed a 2-fold higher severity of symptoms than those of 'Sikitita-2' (21.5% vs. 10.3%, respectively; Table 1). The Logrank test, which compares the time onset in symptoms on the inoculated fruits, further confirmed significant ($P < 0.001$) genotype differences. According to Kaplan-Meier percentiles, half of the drupes from the advanced selection UC-I 6-9 exhibited disease symptoms within 16 days after inoculation with the *C. nymphaeae* isolate. In contrast, a more extended period (37 days) was required to reach a similar incidence on fruits of 'Sikitita' and 'Sikitita-2'. When the different genotypes were inoculated with the *C. godetiae* isolate, significant ($P \leq 0.05$) differences in their resistance were also observed. The fruit of the genotypes UC-I 6-9, UC-I 44-69, UC-I 7-8, and 'Martina' were the most susceptible, with disease severity ranging from 54.1% to 98.2%, while the fruits of 'Picual'

showed a susceptibility of 12.6%. Conversely, 'Picual' fruits showed similar resistance to the drupes of the other genotypes tested such as 'Arbequina', UC-I 33-23, 'Sikitita', UC-I 42-61 or 'Hojiblanca'. Once again, Kaplan-Meier survival analysis revealed significant differences among genotypes ($P < 0.001$), i.e., the difference between cultivars was also appreciated according to the time of appearance of symptoms (incubation period). Again, half of the drupes from the advanced selection UC-I 6-9 showed disease symptoms within 16 days following inoculation with *C. godetiae*, whereas 'Picual' and 'Arbequina' fruits showed similar symptoms 21 days later.

Pathogenic interaction between commercial olive fruit cultivars and *Colletotrichum* species

The results of the cross-inoculation of olive fruits of the main cultivars 'Hojiblanca' and 'Picual' and *C. acutatum*, *C. fioriniae*, *C. nymphaeae*, and *C. godetiae* are presented in Table 2. Initial symptoms (survival percentile 90%) manifested after 12 days of incubation on fruits of both cultivars inoculated with *C. acutatum*, *C. nymphaeae*, or *C. godetiae*. Conversely, 10% of 'Hojiblanca' drupes inoculated with *C. fioriniae* exhibited symptoms 24 days after inoculation, suggesting a delayed fruit colonization rate by this species. Differences ($P \leq 0.05$) were found between the *Colletotrichum* species and the cultivars, but there was no significant interaction between the two independent variables ($P = 0.163$). *C. fioriniae* isolate showed reduced virulence ($P \leq 0.05$) compared to the other species (*C. acutatum*, *C. godetiae*, and *C. nymphaeae*), which did not differ significantly ($P > 0.05$) among themselves (Table 2). Kaplan-Meier percentile values indicated slower fruit colonization by *C. fioriniae* isolates. In 'Picual', half of the fruits showed symptoms 20 days after inoculation with *C. acutatum*, *C. godetiae*, or *C. nymphaeae*; conversely, for *C.*

florinae, the same percentage of affected fruits (50%) was reached after 24 days. A similar reaction was observed in 'Hojiblanca' (Table 2). Overall, 'Picual' drupes displayed a higher resistance ($P = 0.015$) to the pathogen species than 'Hojiblanca,' although differences were less marked than expected (Table 2).

Variability in susceptibility to *C. godetiae* and *C. nymphaeae* in olive leaves of six commercial cultivars

The isolate of the species *C. nymphaeae* demonstrated a more remarkable ability to colonize and induce symptoms in olive leaves than that of *C. godetiae* (Table 3). Specifically, *C. nymphaeae* exhibited higher virulence concerning three dependent variables studied: necrotic leaf surface, leaves with acervuli, and pathogen isolation. Overall, these dependent variables were highly correlated. When young leaves were inoculated, *C. nymphaeae* caused an average of 58.3% necrotic tissue, whereas only 7.6% necrotic area was observed on leaves inoculated with *C. godetiae*. Notably, *C. nymphaeae* developed asexual fruiting bodies (acervuli) with conidia in over 10% of the inoculated leaves (13.6% in old leaves and 8.3% in young leaves), while *C. godetiae* developed some acervuli at a 10-fold lower rate (Fig. 2). Results indicated that young leaves were more susceptible to both species than old leaves in all combinations examined. No correlation was observed when analyzing the olive leaf reaction of the six cultivars and correlating them with our previous data on fruit susceptibility to the pathogen (Spearman correlations $P > 0.05$; Table 3). For example, when comparing the highly susceptible cultivar Ocal, characterized by drupes highly susceptible to the pathogen even in their unripe stage, with the highly resistant cultivar 'Frantoio,' whose drupes exhibit near immunity and even ripen, the susceptibility behavior of their leaves was the

opposite. Interestingly, the pathogen was also readily isolated from inoculated, surface-disinfected leaves, suggesting an increased ability to colonize leaves even in non-symptomatic cultivars, as observed in the study. However, *C. nymphaeae* again showed a higher ability for leaf colonization than *C. godetiae* when this parameter was considered.

Discussion

The experiments in this study unveiled the resistance responses of traditional Spanish olive cultivars and new genotypes to different *Colletotrichum* species. The reactions of the olive genotypes were compared using disease parameters: disease severity over the observation period (rAUDPC) and survival percentiles to evaluate the time to visual symptoms (Madden et al., 2007; Scherm and Ojiambo, 2004). Both variables identified varying responses to the pathogen among olive genotypes, but differences in disease susceptibility among cultivars were more consistently observed concerning disease severity.

Our previous classification highlighted the prevalence of susceptible cultivars, emphasizing the need to identify resistant cultivars or to generate them through breeding programs (Moral et al., 2017). Traditional cultivars such as 'Arbequina' and 'Picual', which are widely grown in Spain (around 620.000 hectares), are common progenitors in breeding programs, given their remarkable agronomic traits, such as oil quality and content and early production (Rallo et al., 2018). However, 'Arbequina' and 'Picual' differ in their susceptibility to aerial fungal diseases and soil-borne pathogens (Moral et al., 2015; Roca et al., 2016). While 'Picual' fruits are considered resistant to *C. godetiae* under controlled and field conditions, 'Arbequina' drupes are moderately susceptible to the pathogen (Moral and Trapero 2009; Moral et al., 2017). In recent decades, 'Arbequina'

has gained enormous global significance due to its good performance in super high-density plantations (hedgerow system) (Rallo et al., 2018). The new cultivar 'Sikitita' (syn. 'Chiquitita'), also well-suited for hedgerow plantations, was released to compete. However, 'Sikitita' fruits are also susceptible to the pathogen and suffer from a significant anthracnose epidemic in seasons with early fruit ripening (J. Moral, *unpublished data*). In the present study, 'Arbequina' and 'Sikitita' fruits showed similar susceptibility to the pathogen, but specific genotype-pathogen interactions were detected. This is a matter of concern, given the conducive conditions for the disease resulting from the increased wetness duration on the olive canopy due to the new cultivation system (Moral et al., 2012).

Our study, which focused on the susceptibility variation among 52 genotypes (F1 from the cross 'Arbequina' × 'Picual') and seven advanced selections under laboratory conditions, presented new and intriguing results. This progeny displayed variable susceptibility to *C. godetiae*, with no completely resistant genotypes identified. However, this lack of assured resistance in the progeny is consistent with the expected outcome of a polygenic trait. Such differential susceptibility patterns have been observed in various studies screening olive genotypes against necrotrophic fungi, highlighting the broad segregation potential among the progeny of olive cultivars due to their high heterozygosity. These results, while challenging, also offer hope for developing resistant cultivars in the future.

Variations in susceptibility among new cultivars and advanced selections were compared with the commercial cvs. Arbequina, Hojiblanca, Picual, and Sikitita. In particular, the fruits of the new cultivar 'Sikitita-2' showed a disease severity 2-fold lower

than that of the cv. Picual, which was considered resistant. However, the low proportion of resistant genotypes among the advanced selections could be due to the lack of early screening tests to assess seedlings for anthracnose resistance since fruit production is required for inoculation (Moral et al., 2015; 2017). In any case, cultivar reaction to *Colletotrichum* is a continuous variable, ranging from highly susceptible to highly resistant cultivars, but none of the used progenitors showed complete resistance (Moral and Trapero 2009). Previously, we evaluated the resistance of ‘Martina’, UC-I 7-8, and UC-I 6-9 and classified them as susceptible but only against the dominant species in Spain, *C. godetiae*. Considering that these new cultivars may be extended to other olive-growing regions, such as Portugal, where the dominant species is *C. nymphaeae* (Talhinhas et al., 2018), we evaluated them against both species, classifying them as susceptible or highly susceptible. However, the ‘Sikitita-2’ drupes showed important changes in response depending on the pathogen species. Previously, Talhinhas et al. (2015) and Riolo et al. (2022), working with Portuguese and Italian traditional cultivars, described significant interactions between cultivars and *Colletotrichum* species. In addition, the resistance of the fruit is well known to be highly dependent on its phenological stage, which is influenced by peel color, but also by the color of the mesocarp. Thus, fruits of a given genotype showing the same peel color could show different resistance levels (Moral and Trapero, 2009; Miho et al., 2023). For this reason, we use numerous fruits as pseudo-replicates to reduce this source of variation (Moral and Trapero, 2009). Recent studies have shown that olive fruit undergoes substantial metabolic chemical changes during ripening, influencing the composition of phenolic compounds, which determine susceptibility to *Colletotrichum* spp. (Miho et al., 2023).

Our study explored the interaction between olive cultivars ('Picual' as resistant and 'Hojiblanca' as susceptible) and four *Colletotrichum* spp. (*C. acutatum*, *C. fioriniae*, *C. nymphaeae*, and *C. godetiae*). Our results revealed that the isolate of the species *C. fioriniae* was weakly virulent, causing minor symptoms, in contrast to the other species, which were highly virulent and showed no difference. Nevertheless, both 'Hojiblanca' and 'Picual' proved susceptible to all four *Colletotrichum* spp., albeit varying degrees. Prior studies have highlighted the higher virulence of certain species belonging to the *C. acutatum* complex, indicating their adaptability to different agro-climatic conditions and specific hosts. Thus, with some differences, probably due to the experimental process and the isolate, these studies indicate that *C. acutatum*, *C. godetiae*, and *C. nymphaeae* are highly virulent compared to other species such as *C. fioriniae*, *C. gloeosporioides*, or *C. karsti* (Garcia-Lopez et al., 2023; Moral et al., 2021; Schena et al., 2017; Talhinhos et al., 2015). In contrast, according to Riolo et al. (2023b), only the species *C. nymphaeae* and *C. acutatum* caused symptoms on unwounded drupes but with a short incubation period (≤ 14 days). To date, *C. godetiae* has been demonstrated to be pathogenic on unwounded olive fruits with varying levels of virulence in many cases (Moral et al., 2015, 2017; Garcia-Lopez et al., 2023; Talhinhos et al., 2018). However, variability within isolates of this species has also been described (Moral et al., 2021).

Finally, we studied the variability in susceptibility to *C. godetiae* and *C. nymphaeae* in leaves of six commercial olive cultivars, exploring the potential of olive leaves as a significant inoculum source (Garcia-Lopez et al., 2023; Talhinhos et al., 2011). In particular, *C. nymphaeae* demonstrated a remarkable ability to colonize and produce acervuli in olive leaves, while *C. godetiae* showed limited acervuli production. This supports previous findings suggesting that leaves act, in addition to fruits, as a significant

inoculum source during the epidemic season in Portugal, where *C. nymphaeae* is predominant (Talhinhas et al., 2011), while rotten fruits serve as the main inoculum source in Spain, where *C. godetiae* is the causal agent (Moral and Trapero 2012). Thus, the differences in pathogen populations between Spain and Portugal may account for the differences in anthracnose epidemics between the two countries (Moral et al., 2009; Moral and Trapero, 2012; Talhinhas et al., 2011; 2018). In field monitoring in southern Spain, we have observed the development of anthracnose in olives in the absence of mummified fruit in the canopy (J. Moral, *unpublished data*), which could be explained by the role of the leaf as a source of inoculum, by alloinfection processes, or the role of the olive fruit fly (*Bactrocera olea*) as a spore carrier (Malacrinò et al., 2015). Moreover, due to the lack of a correlation between leaf and fruit susceptibility of a given genotype to the pathogen, it is necessary to use fruits to evaluate new genotypes for anthracnose resistance until the development of molecular markers that allow early genotype selection. However, achieving this seems challenging, as other studies indicate that resistance is highly dependent on secondary compounds of fruit metabolism rather than specific genes (Miho et al., 2023).

In summary, the insights into the resistance of olive genotypes to *Colletotrichum* species and our new findings on the role of leaves in the epidemic not only enhance our understanding of the olive anthracnose but also lay the groundwork for developing comprehensive management strategies. Complementary to fungicide use, these strategies are essential for the sustainability of olive crops.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could appear to have influenced the work reported in this paper.

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Table 1. Susceptibility of seven advanced selections and four olive cultivars to *Colletotrichum godetiae* and *C. nymphaeae* expressed in disease severity (rAUDPC) and Kaplan-Maier survival time percentiles.

<i>Colletotrichum</i> specie	Genotype	Genitors ^x ♀ × ♂	Disease severity (rAUDPC) ^y	Survival time percentiles (%) ^z				
				10	25	50	75	90
<i>C. godetiae</i>	'Picual'		12.7 f	37	37	37	30	23
	'Hojiblanca'		24.9 de	37	37	30	30	23
	'Sikitita'	P × A	22.1 def	37	37	30	30	23
	'Arbequina'		17.5 ef	37	37	37	30	23
	UC-I 44-69	P (O.P.)	78.3 b	30	23	23	16	9
	UC-I 42-61	P × A	24.1 def	37	37	30	30	23
	UC-I 33-23	A (O.P.)	21.7 def	37	37	30	30	23
	UC-I 7-8	A × P	63.2 c	37	37	30	23	16
	UC-I 6-9	A × P	98.2 a	23	23	16	9	9
	'Martina'	P × A	54.1 c	30	30	23	23	16
'Sikitita-2'	A × P	32.6 d	37	37	30	23	23	
	Mean		40.9					
<i>C. nymphaeae</i>	'Picual'		21.5 fg	37	37	30	30	23
	'Hojiblanca'		29.4 ef	37	37	30	23	23
	'Sikitita'	P × A	20.3 fg	>37	37	37	30	23
	'Arbequina'		37.7 de	37	37	30	23	16

						Anabel Exposito <i>Plant Disease</i>		
UC-I 44-69	P (O.P.)	64.0 c	30	30	23	16	16	
UC-I 42-61	P × A	46.2 d	37	37	30	23	16	
UC-I 33-23	A (O.P.)	68.6 bc	23	23	23	16	16	
UC-I 7-8	A × P	84.4 b	30	30	23	16	9	
UC-I 6-9	A × P	103.1 a	16	16	16	9	9	
'Martina'	P × A	38.8 de	37	37	30	23	23	
'Sikitita-2'	A × P	10.3 g	>37	>37	37	37	30	
Mean		47.6						

^xP= Picual; A=Arbequina; O.P.= open-pollination.

^yThe relative area under the disease progression curve (rAUDPC) was calculated by trapezoidal integration of the disease intensity values over 30 days. Different letters in the same column indicate significant differences within mean values for each *Colletotrichum* species according to the Least Significant Differences test at $P \leq 0.05$

^zEstimated Kaplan-Meier survival time percentiles (days) at 10, 25, 50, 75, and 90% over 37 days after inoculation. Percentiles were compared using the nonparametric Logrank test with differences at $P < 0.001$.

Table 2. Susceptibility of cultivars ‘Hojiblanca’ and ‘Picual’ to *Colletotrichum acutatum*, *C. fioriniae*, *C. godetiae*, and *C. nymphaeae* expressed in disease severity and Kaplan-Maier survival time percentiles.

Cultivar	<i>Colletotrichum</i> species	Disease severity (rAUDPC) ^y	Survival time percentiles (%) ^z				
			10	25	50	75	90
‘Picual’	<i>C. godetiae</i>	38.9 a	24	24	20	16	12
	<i>C. nymphaeae</i>	40.2 a	24	24	20	16	12
	<i>C. acutatum</i>	33.8 a	24	24	20	16	12
	<i>C. fioriniae</i>	2.8 b	>24	>24	24	20	12
Mean		28.9 B					
‘Hojiblanca’	<i>C. godetiae</i>	42.2 a	24	24	20	16	12
	<i>C. nymphaeae</i>	45.3 a	24	24	20	16	12
	<i>C. acutatum</i>	35.3 a	24	24	20	16	12
	<i>C. fioriniae</i>	19.5 b	>24	>24	>24	>24	24
Mean		35.6 A					

^yRelative Area Under the Disease Progress Curve (rAUDPC) was calculated by trapezoidal integration of the disease intensity values over 30 days. Different letters in the

same column indicate significant differences within mean values for each *Colletotrichum* species according to the Least Significant Differences (LSD) test at $P \leq 0.05$.

^z Kaplan-Meier survival time percentile estimates (days) at 10, 25, 50, 75 and 90%. Percentiles were compared using the nonparametric Logrank test, showing differences at $P < 0.001$.

Table 3. Percentages of necrotic leaf area, leaves with acervuli, and leaf pathogen isolation of young and old leaves of six olive cultivars inoculated with *Colletotrichum nymphaeae* and *C. godetiae*.

Pathogen/Cultivar	Affected Leaf necrotic fruits (%) ^x		Leaves with acervuli (%) ^{y z}		Leaf pathogen isolation (%) ^{y z}		
	Young	Old	Young	Old	Young	Old	
<i>C. nymphaeae</i>							
'Arbequina'	9,1	66,7ab	20,8bc	16,7a	5,0bc	100a	65,0b
'Frantoio'	0,1	4,2b	8,3bc	1,7b	1,7c	86,7a	86,7ab
'Hojiblanca'	87,8	87,5a	37,5abc	18,3a	6,7bc	100a	75,0ab
'Ocal'	91,8	4,2b	0,0c	1,7b	0,0c	86,7a	23,3c
'Picual'	1,9	91,7a	45,8ab	23,3a	13,3ab	100a	90,0ab
'Sikitita'	3,6	95,8a	91,7a	20,0a	23,3a	95,3a	100,0a
Mean		58,3A	34,0A	13,6A	8,3A	100A	73,3A
<i>C. godetiae</i>							
'Arbequina'	9,1	0,0b	0,0c	0,0a	0,0a	37,5ab	17,5cd
'Frantoio'	0,1	0,0b	0,0c	0,0a	0,0a	46,7a	43,3bc
'Hojiblanca'	87,8	0,0b	20,8a	0,0a	3,3a	45,0a	95,0a

						Anabel Exposito <i>Plant Disease</i>	
'Ocal'	91,8	0,0b	0,0c	0,0a	0,0a	16,7b	5,0d
'Picual'	1,9	16,7ab	0,0c	5,0a	0,0a	73,8a	22,5cd
'Sikitita'	3,6	29,2a	8,3ab	5,0a	1,7a	65,0a	56,7b
Mean		7.6B	4,9B	1,7B	0,8B	49.4B	40,3B

^xPercentage of fruit rot incidence caused by *Colletotrichum* spp. under field conditions according to Moral et al. (2017)

^yYoung and old olive leaves were inoculated using conidial suspensions (2×10^5 conidia/ml, 0.4 ml per leaf) of *C. godetiae* or *C. nymphaeae*.

^z In each column and for each *Colletotrichum* species means with the same letter are not significantly different based on the Least Significant Differences (LSD) at $P \leq 0.05$.

Similarly, species means with the same letter are not significantly different (LSD) at $P \leq 0.05$.

Figure Legend

Fig. 1. Frequency distribution of disease severity, evaluated as the relative Area Under the Disease Progress Curve, caused by *Colletotrichum godetiae* in olive fruits of 52 F₁ progenies derived from the cross 'Picual' × 'Arbequina'. Each column indicates the number of progenies with similar disease severity, expressed as a percentage of the frequency. According to Shapiro-Wilk's test, the data followed a normal distribution (line).

Fig. 2. A: *Colletotrichum nymphaeae* acervuli (red arrows) and trichomes (green arrows) in an olive leaf of the cultivar Hojiblanca. B: *C. nymphaeae* acervuli in an olive leaf of the cultivar Sikitita.

